

Service Provider User Story Analysis - RDA Minimal MD

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Service provider wanting to promote their training resources (SP-1)								
2	Service Provider wanting to know where gaps are in subject coverage (SP-2)								
3	Service provider wanting to provide an overview of training possibilities for their community (SP-3)								
4	Generic Term	Description	Metadata req (SP-1)	Useful for Extended Doc (SP-1)	Metadata req (SP-2)	Useful for Extended Doc (SP-2)	Metadata req (SP-3)	Useful for Extended Doc (SP-3)	Comment / Notes
5	title	The name of the resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
6	abstract	A brief overview of the item (container)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
7	abstract_data	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	either an abstract or description would be needed. But probably not both?
8	access_cost	Choice stating whether or not there is a fee for use of the resource (Boolean).	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Assumes that researcher wants to filter by free or not. May vary by user. Suggest information about variations in fees be included in the Description field, e.g., student may access a resource w/o fee, but a researcher may be req to pay.
9	author(s)	List of full name of the author(s)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
10	author.familyName	Last or family name of person(s) authoring the resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
11	author.givenName	First or given name of person(s) authoring the resource	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
12	author_org	Name of organization authoring the resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
13	contributor(s)	List of full name of secondary person(s) contributing to the resource.	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	
14	contributor_orgs.name	Name of contributing organization(s)	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	
15	contributor_orgs.type	Type of contribution made by the organization	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Use CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy)?
16	contributors.familyName	Family or last name of the contributor.	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	
17	contributors.givenName	Given or first name of contributor(s)	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	

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18	name_identifier	The unique identifier for individual or organization referenced.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Useful for FAIR, if available.
19	name_type	The name of the identifier scheme.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
20	contributors.type	Type of contribution made by a person or organization.	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Clarify whether this is only for a person contributor
21	contribution_date	Date of the contribution to the resource	N	N	N	N	N	N	
22	contribution_entity	Identification of and information about entities (i.e., people, organizations) contributing to the resource	N	N	N	N	N	N	
23	language_primary	Language in which the resource was originally published or made available.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
24	languages_secondary	Additional languages in which the resource is available, if any.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Assumes, if applicable.
25	keywords	Keywords or tags used to describe the resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
26	license	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Necessary for FAIR
27	lr_type	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
28	target_audience	Principle users(s) for which the resource was designed.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	May not be necessary if LR is created for a particular community or institution (i.e. a research institute vs. a general catalogue)
29	subject	Subject domain toward which the resource is targeted.	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Some resources are too generic for subject specificity
30	skill_level	Target skill level in the topic being taught; example values include: beginner, intermediate, advanced.	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	
31	typical_age_range	The typical range of ages for the content's intended end user.	N	N	N	N	N	N	
32	difficulty	How hard it is to work with or through the resource for the typical intended target audience (very easy, easy, medium, difficult, very difficult, knowledge-dependent)	N	N	N	N	N	N	this relates to skill_level further down the list. Both might not be needed.

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33	published	Date of publication / broadcast.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	- might help with choice if more than one topic
34	modification_date	Date at which the educational resource was most recently published or broadcast.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Emphasis upon publication /broadcast here, but should be considered with other dates, e.g., creation & publication dates
35	version	The specific version of the resource, if declared.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
36	publisher	The organization credited with publishing or broadcasting the resource (does not include the repository where resource is stored).	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	- reputation of organisation may be important; what about shared publishing in terms of repeatability?
37	url	URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
38	usage_info	Text describing information about using the resource, not addressed by the license URL.	N	y	N	y	N	Y	Would be place for adding attribution info (rather than "is-based-on-url above; row 50).
39	usage_restrictions	Yes / No response to whether copyright or other restrictions apply to the use of the resource	N	N	N	N	N	N	If no other info is available about copyright or licensing, could use this.
40	use_rights_url	The URL where the owner specifies permissions for using the resource	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	R	If no other info is available about copyright or licensing, should use this as some information is req for FAIR at least.
41	learning_outcome	Descriptions of what knowledge, skills or abilities students should acquire on completion of the resource.	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	
42	citation	Preferred form of citation	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	
43	locator.data	From DC "An unambiguous reference to the resources within a given context." Use a string that conforms to an ID system. See how FAIRsFAIR deals with this...	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Could be the same as the persistent ID for the resource.

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44	locator.type	Controlled vocabulary designating the persistent identifier schemes used for the resource, e.g., DOI, ARK, Handle.	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Should be used with the citable locator.
45	completion_time	Approximate or typical time it takes to work with or through the resource for the typical, intended target audience.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	This maybe important when making a decision but probably isn't necessary in all cases;
46	completion_status	Completion status or condition of the resource (draft, final, revised, unavailable)	N	N	N	N	N	N	But versioning would be helpful;could be useful from an internal system POV
47	interactivity_level	Degree of interactivity characterizing the resource; refers to the degree to which the learner can influence the aspect of behavior of resource (e.g., very low, low, medium, high, very high).	N	N	N	N	N	N	Indicates student amount of effort req;
48	interactivity_type	The predominant mode of learning supported by the learning resource (i.e., active, expositive, or mixed)	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	
49	credential_status	Type of credentialing offered for the resource, if any.	N	N	N	N	N	N	Would need to explain the issues associated with declaring a credential (from whom, authority, academic or occupational, etc.)
50	contact	Name of person who has been asserted as the contact(s) for the resource in case of questions or follow-up by resource user.	Recmnd	y	Recmnd	y	Recmnd	Y	
51	email	Email address of person or organization that has been asserted as the contact for the resource.	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	1 to 1 relationship for each contact name; preferred address is most stable (persistent).
52	org	Name of organization that has been asserted as the contact for the resource in case of questions or follow-up by resource user.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	
53	media_type	From schema.org def: "Media type of resource, typically expressed using a MIME format" from IANA site & MDN reference.	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	Y	Useful for FAIR?

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54	ed_frameworks.name	The name of an framework to which the resource is aligned, if any.	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Need to discuss if / how this relates to skill competence framework (e.g., FAIR4S)
55	ed_frameworks.nodes.description	The description of a node in an educational framework	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	
56	ed_frameworks.nodes.name	The name of a node in an established educational framework.	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	
57	ed_frameworks.nodes.url	The URL of a node in an established educational framework.	N	N	N	N	N	N	
58	ed_frameworks.url	The URL of an established educational framework	N	N	N	N	N	N	
59	alignment_type	A category of alignment between the learning resource and the framework node. (See notes for Recmnd values).	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	
60	hasPart	A sub-Training resource or externally referenced resource	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Possibly one to many
61	isPartOf	Course in which this resource was/will be used, or the resource in which this resource is a part (e.g., part of a book or slide-set associated with a course).	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Many to one
62	is_based_on_url	A resource that was used in the creation of this resource (repeatable)	N	N	N	N	N	N	Attribution info included in usage information below. (row 85).
63	resource_size	Size of the resource in bytes (uncompressed)	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Important for downloadable resource.
64	accessibility_control	Indicates input methods that are sufficient to fully control the described resource (CV list of values at https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	

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65	accessibility_features	Content features of the resource, such as accessible media, alternatives and supported enhancements for accessibility (WebSchemas wiki lists possible values). Only 4 values of the entire list were available in the drupal production system; others are to be added to the CV for this field as called for.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	
66	accessibility_hazard	A characteristic of the described resource that is physiologically dangerous to some users. (CV list of values at: https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	N	N	N	N	N	
67	accessibility_summary	Human readable summary of accessibility features and deficiencies	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	
68	accessibility_api	Indicates that the resource is compatible with the referenced accessibility API (CV list of values at https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	N	N	N	N	N	
69	date_created	The date on which the resource was created.	N	N	N	N	N	N	- if topic is likely to have changed
70	country_of_origin	Code for country from which resource was generated;	N	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	would depend on whether the topic is country specific e.g. legislation or speak to language translatability
71	coverage	Time, culture, geography or region to which this learning object applies. The extent or scope of its content. Coverage will typically include spatial location (a place name or geographic coordinates), temporal period (a period label, date, or date range) or jurisdiction (such as a named administrative entity).	N	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	would depend on whether the topic is country specific e.g. legislation or speak to language translatability

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72	mentions	Data-sets, tools, technologies, entities, other training materials in the series, etc., to which the resource makes reference. **	N	N	N	N	N	N	Ambiguous term; is this duplicative of others?
73	context	Principal environment within which the learning & use of the resource is intended to take place, e.g., school, higher education, etc.	N	Recmnd	Y	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	would depend on whether the topic is country specific e.g. legislation or speak to language translatability
74	purpose	The purpose of the work in the context of education.	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Ambiguous term;
75	uses	Data-sets, tools, technologies, entites, etc. that are actively utilised in this resource.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	
76	rating	Placeholder for comments given by users assessing the educational resource after use.	N	N	N	N	N	N	
77	ratings	If applicable, placeholder for overall ratings for the educational resource, based on a collection of reviews or ratings.	N	N	N	N	N	N	Aggregation of rating comments.
78	semantic_density	Degree of conciseness; may be estimated in terms of its size, span or duration	N	N	N	N	N	N	Related to interactivity level. May be difficult to discern.
79	System MD fields below:								
80	id	System identifier for the MD record.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	System field
81	md_record_id	Globally unique, persistent ID for the metadata record within the system for the resource being described.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Necessary for FAIR; should be in the form of a resolvable ID, e.g., DOI, Handle, ARK, LSID, etc.
82	submitter_email	Person submitting the resource into the DMTC queue for publication.	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Not necessary for discovery; useful for admin/system
83	submitter_name	Email address of person submitting the resource into the DMTC queue for publication.	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Not necessary for discovery; useful for admin/system
84	created	The date on which the metadata record was created.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	System field
85	creator	The login name of the person creating the MD record.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	System field
86	featured_event	Course instance or event where this training resource was or will be featured. (inverse of workFeatured)	N	N	N	N	N	N	Events out of scope.

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87									
88									
89	resource_id_label	A globally unique label that identifies the learning object.							Used by ENVRI LOM: identifier (General 1.1)
90	resource_id_scheme	Name or designator of the identification or cataloging scheme for the globally unique label (resource ID)							Used by ENVRI LOM: catalog (General 1.2)
91	resource_id_value	Value of the identifier within the identification or cataloging scheme that designates or identifies the learning object. Should be a namespace specific string.							Used by ENVRI LOM: entry (General 1.3)
92									
93	REFERENCES								
94	* Taken from https://zenodo.org/record/3903341 (ENVRI LOM profile)								
95	** Taken from https://bioschemas.org/profiles/TrainingMaterial/0.7-DRAFT-2019_11_08/								